

Enabling Open Science Through Research Code

Episode 5: Testing Research Code

Session information

Webpage	https://rsse.africa/events-rsse-africa/2025-02-20/
Date	20 February 2025
Time	08:30 - 10:00 am UTC (your time zone)
Facilitators	Jyoti Bhogal Anelda van der Walt
Co-facilitators	Mireille Grobbelaar
Speakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Abhishek Dasgupta● Saranjeet Kaur● Sheena O'Connell
Zoom registration	https://us06web.zoom.us/meeting/register/tZArd-GvqzkiGt13BRkC_V_4mAla0uRWeGqeE

Schedule

Time	Activity	Speakers
8:30 UTC	Giving everyone time to join	Facilitator: Anelda
8:35 UTC	Welcome	Facilitator: Anelda
8:40 UTC	Introduction to Testing Research Code	Facilitator: Jyoti
8:50 UTC	Introducing our speakers <i>Tell us a bit about your background and your current role?</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What did you study and where? ○ Do you have postgrad qualifications? In what area? ○ What is the title of your current role? ○ Give a one-sentence summary of what you do in this role 	Facilitator: Jyoti Abhishek Dasgupta Saranjeet Kaur Sheena O'Connell
9:10 UTC	Polls	Facilitator: Anelda
9:15 UTC	Panel discussion 1. What is software testing? 2. How can software testing improve research reproducibility and collaboration? 3. What are the most useful types of tests for research code? (e.g., unit tests, integration tests, regression tests, property-based tests)	Facilitator: Anelda Abhishek Dasgupta Saranjeet Kaur Sheena O'Connell Facilitator: Jyoti Abhishek Dasgupta

Time	Activity	Speakers
	<p>4. What are some lightweight testing strategies that researchers with minimal programming experience can use?</p> <p>5. If someone has never written a test before, what is the simplest way to start?</p> <p>6. How can version control (e.g., Git) and continuous integration (CI) help automate testing in research projects?</p> <p>7. What tools and frameworks would you recommend for testing in common research languages (Python, R, MATLAB, etc.)?</p> <p>8. How can researchers balance the trade-off between writing tests and meeting research deadlines?</p>	<p>Saranjeet Kaur Sheena O'Connell</p> <p>Abhishek Dasgupta Sheena O'Connell</p> <p>Facilitator: Anelda</p> <p>Abhishek Dasgupta Saranjeet Kaur Sheena O'Connell</p> <p>Abhishek Dasgupta Saranjeet Kaur Sheena O'Connell</p> <p>Facilitator: Jyoti</p> <p>Abhishek Dasgupta Saranjeet Kaur</p>
9:55 UTC	Wrap-up and next steps	Facilitator: Anelda

Resources and info from partners

RSSE Africa

- Website: <https://rsse.africa>
- Sign up for our newsletter:
<https://talarify.us14.list-manage.com/subscribe?u=35d5db26d3b108b9ef9b9ac43&iid=55e9f5a692>
- Join our LinkedIn group, where you can also share information with the broader community: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12903402/>

RSE Asia

- Website: https://rse-asia.github.io/RSE_Asia/
- For the latest news, events, activities, and opportunities, follow us on our [LinkedIn page](https://www.linkedin.com/company/rse-asia-association/) (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/rse-asia-association/>)
- To join the RSE Asia community, please fill out our short [Community Membership Form](https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1XSxDaTJzcNyGeDYXyJNVg1TDCo7un18PLFNiK6_jL2g/edit) (https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1XSxDaTJzcNyGeDYXyJNVg1TDCo7un18PLFNiK6_jL2g/edit)

AREN

- Website: <https://africanrn.org/>
- Sign up:
<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeeFkD5A4D9l6ncQWjKBil-GqBOzL-JMe7Fx3ijUYEjHjDUoQ/viewform>

ReSA

- Website: <https://www.researchsoft.org/>
- Sign up for the newsletter: <https://www.researchsoft.org/news/>
- The [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability](#)
 - Become a signatory: <https://adore.software/sign/>

Shared resources from the session

Workshops & Conferences

- [Guild of Educators](#) – A professional organization focused on educational excellence and development.
- [ISCB Africa 2025](#) – International Society for Computational Biology's Africa conference on bioinformatics and computational biology.

Software Testing & Quality Assurance

- [Essential Software Engineering for Researchers – Testing Overview](#) – Introduction to software testing and its importance in research software engineering.
- [Hypothesis Documentation](#) – A Python library for property-based testing, helping to generate test cases automatically.
- [fusen R Package](#) – An R package for structuring and testing software code.
- [Software Assertions \(Wikipedia\)](#) – Overview of assertions, an essential part of defensive programming and testing.
- [pytest Guide \(Real Python\)](#) – A comprehensive guide to pytest, a popular Python testing framework.
- [GeeksforGeeks: Unit Testing](#) – Explanation of unit testing concepts and their role in software testing.
- [nbval Documentation](#) – A pytest plugin for validating Jupyter notebooks by running their code cells.
- [nbval GitHub Repository](#) – The GitHub repository for the nbval plugin, which integrates Jupyter notebooks with pytest.
- [pytest Documentation](#) – Official documentation for pytest, covering installation and usage.
- [{checkmate} R Package](#) – An R package for runtime testing and validation.
- [Code Testing – The Turing Way](#) – An introduction to best practices for writing and running tests in research software.
- [PyCharm Blog: pytest vs unittest](#) – A comparison of two major Python testing frameworks.
- [CodeRefinery Testing Guide](#) – A structured guide to software testing principles and tools for researchers.
- [Good Developers, Bad Tests](#) – A blog post discussing common pitfalls in writing software tests.

Continuous Integration & Development Workflows

- [GitHub Actions Overview](#) – A guide to automating workflows using GitHub Actions.
- [GitLab CI/CD](#) – GitLab's guide to setting up continuous integration and deployment.
- [Bitbucket Pipelines](#) – Atlassian's CI/CD tool for Bitbucket repositories.
- [Life Before Version Control \(PhD Comics\)](#) – A humorous take on research code management before version control systems.
- [GitHub Actions for Research Software](#) – Documentation on writing workflows for automated testing and deployment.
- [usethis R Package](#) – A set of R functions to simplify project setup and GitHub integration.
- [usethis GitHub Actions](#) – Guide to automating R workflows with GitHub Actions.

- [Pandera – Data Validation for Pandas](#) – A Python package for schema validation of Pandas dataframes.
- [R testthat Package](#) – The most popular R package for unit testing.
- [C++ Testing Frameworks](#) – Overview of testing frameworks such as GoogleTest, Boost Test, and Catch2.
- [Fortran Testing Tools](#) – Includes tools like Test-Drive and pFUnit for writing unit tests in Fortran.
- [Machine Learning Mastery: Statistical Tests](#) – A cheat sheet for statistical hypothesis testing in Python.
- [SciPy Statistical Tests](#) – SciPy’s reference guide for statistical functions.
- [tox Testing Framework](#) – A Python tool for testing code across multiple environments.
- [pytest-xdist](#) – A pytest extension for running tests in parallel.
- [Technical Debt \(Wikipedia\)](#) – An overview of technical debt and its impact on software development.

Relevant publications & blog posts

- Eisty, N. U., Kanewala, U., & Carver, J. C. (2025). Testing Research Software: An In-Depth Survey of Practices, Methods, and Tools. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.17739*. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2501.17739v1>
- Stephan Ferenz, Emilie Frost, Rico Schrage, Thomas Wolgast, Inga Beyers, Oliver Karras, Oliver Werth, Astrid Nieße. (2025). Ten Recommendations for Engineering Research Software in Energy Research. *arXiv preprint. arXiv:2502.13510*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2502.13510>
- Blog post: [Building an R package using {fusen}](#), Author: Saranjeet Kaur Bhogal

Upcoming events from around the world

- CodeRefinery workshop March 25-27 and April 1-3, 2025 - <https://coderefinery.github.io/2025-03-25-workshop/>